

Supplementary Material for Research Preview “Explainability as a Requirement for Hardware: Introducing Explainable Hardware (XHW)”

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I. FRAMEWORK COMPONENTS

Stakeholder Categories		Explainability Approaches	
Trusted Manufacturing			
Standards & Certifications			
Open Hardware			
Testing & Verification			
Physical Analysis			

Desiderata			
Security			
Verifiability			
Trust			
Trustworthiness			

Fig. 1. A compact overview of all components considered in our framework.

II. SURVEY TRANSCRIPT

A. Informed Consent

Dear Study Participant,

We as researchers at the Max Planck Institute for Security and Privacy (MPI-SP), Ruhr University Bochum (RUB), and University of Bayreuth (UBT) are conducting a short survey on explainability in the context of modern hardware. The goal of our research and this survey is to determine the applicability of explainability to hardware. By participating in our survey, you will help us to explore this research question.

Filling out the survey takes around 10-15 minutes. Participation in the survey is voluntary. You can terminate your participation at any time and without giving any reasons. All data collected in the survey will be treated confidentially (GDPR on the use of data for scientific purposes). The data collected will be stored and analyzed anonymously. All data collected will be used for scientific purposes only and stored on a server that complies with data protection laws. The results and parts of the data may be published as a scientific publication. This will be done in anonymized form, i.e., without the data being able to be assigned to a specific person. The anonymized data may be made available to others in digitized form in a data archive. Here, too, no information is included that allows conclusions to be drawn about individual participants.

For questions about the survey, please contact Julian Speith (julian.speith@mpi-sp.org) or Steffen Becker (steffen.becker@mpi-sp.org). For questions regarding data protection, please contact the MPI-SP data protection officer, Peter Schwabe (peter.schwabe@mpi-sp.org).

Sincerely yours,

Timo Speith, Julian Speith, Steffen Becker, Yixin Zou, Asia Biega, and Christof Paar

- 1) I agree that I participate in the study and that the data collected in the study may be used for scientific purposes.
 - Yes No
- 2) I agree that the data collected in the study may be made available to other researchers in anonymized form. These scientists will be required to work to the same standards.
 - Yes No

B. Demographic Information

- 3) How old are you? Please select the respective age group.
 - 18-29 years 30-39 years 40-49 years 50-59 years 60-69 years 70 years or older No answer
- 4) What is your gender?
 - Male Female Non-binary Other: [free text] No answer
- 5) What is your highest general education degree?
 - No school leaving certificate Secondary school diploma (“Hauptschulabschluss”) or equivalent qualification Secondary school diploma (“Realschulabschluss”) or

- equivalent qualification ◦ High school diploma (“Abitur”) or university entrance qualification
- 6) What professional educational qualifications do you have? *[Please select all professional qualifications you have obtained to date.]* ◦ No professional qualification and not in vocational training ◦ Currently in training (e.g., trainee, student) ◦ Vocational training / apprenticeship ◦ Graduation from a technical school or administrative or technical academy ◦ Bachelor degree ◦ Diploma or master degree ◦ PhD degree ◦ Other: [free text]
- 7) What is your predominant occupation? ◦ I am gainfully employed or working (incl. apprentices, persons on parental leave or partial retirement) ◦ I am a basic military/civilian service member ◦ I am a pupil ◦ I am a student ◦ I am a retiree, pensioner ◦ I live from income from capital assets, renting or leasing ◦ I am a homemaker or care for children and/or persons in need of care ◦ I am unemployed ◦ None of the above choices (e.g., permanently unable to work) ◦ No answer
- 8) What do you work as? *[In case of multiple activities: Refer to the activity with the highest number of hours per week. In case of interruption of the activity (e.g., due to parental leave, partial retirement): Refer to the interrupted activity.]* ◦ Salaried employee ◦ Blue-collar worker, homemaker ◦ Apprentice ◦ Self-employed persons without employees (including freelancers, persons with a contract for work and services) ◦ Self-employed with employees ◦ Family worker (unpaid activity) ◦ Civil servant, judge, civil service employee ◦ Regular soldier, professional soldier ◦ Basic military/civilian service member ◦ Part-time jobber, 1-Euro jobber
- 9) Please assign the company in which you are or were last employed to an industry/sector. *[If you are not currently employed, please indicate the industry/sector in which you were last employed. Please be guided by the economic focus of your branch of business (not of the entire company). For self-employed persons and part-time workers: If you are not active in any business, please indicate the industry/sector in which you are primarily active as a self-employed person or part-time jobber.]* ◦ Agriculture, forestry and fishing ◦ Manufacturing/production of goods, mining and quarrying, other industry ◦ Construction, civil engineering ◦ Trade, transport and storage, hospitality/accommodation and food services ◦ Information and communication ◦ Banks/financial and insurance service providers ◦ Real estate and housing ◦ Freelance, scientific and technical services and other economic services ◦ Public administration, defense, social security, education, health care and social services ◦ Other services ◦ Other: [free text]
- 10) In which field are you studying? ◦ humanities (e.g., philosophy, theology, history, linguistics or cultural studies) ◦ sports ◦ law, economics, and social sciences ◦ mathematics, natural sciences ◦ human medicine, health sciences ◦ agricultural, forestry and nutritional sciences, veterinary medicine ◦ engineering sciences (e.g., mechan-

ical engineering, electrical engineering and information technology, computer science, architecture, civil engineering, materials science) ◦ art, art science ◦ other: [free text]

C. Explainability of Hardware

Now for the main part of our survey. To determine whether and how explainability can be applied to the hardware domain, we ask you to provide your valuable insights on certain interactions between stakeholders, requirements, and existing approaches by rating them in their importance, applicability, and usefulness. This will help us to identify explainability gaps that are not yet covered by the existing approaches and subsequently stir future research into the respective directions.

Please read the definitions below before you start filling the tables and refer back to them whenever you are uncertain about what is meant by a certain stakeholder category, requirement, or approach.

Stakeholder Categories

Over the course of its lifetime, a variety of stakeholders interact with a hardware-based system. Note that an entity (a person or an organization) can be part of more than one stakeholder category at the same time. Please carefully read the description of each stakeholder category below:

- **Designer:** Designs the hardware (i.e., the chips), describes it in an HDL, synthesizes and implements the design using EDA tools.
- **Manufacturer:** Produces the hardware according to the (synthesized and implemented) design in one of its fabs.
- **System Integrator:** Integrates the manufactured hardware into a larger system (e.g., smartphone, car, ...) comprising other software and hardware components as well.
- **Policy Makers & Watchdogs:** Policy makers introduce laws, regulations, and standards concerning design, manufacturing, integration, and use of hardware. Watchdogs ensure that designers, manufacturers and system integrators adhere to these laws, regulations, and standards.
- **End Users:** Either uses a system directly (e.g., smartphone, car) or operates a system (e.g., telecommunication provider, railway operator).

Requirements

Each stakeholder has a unique set of requirements concerning a hardware-based system. Please carefully read the description of each relevant requirement below:

- **Debuggability:** Easily identify, trace and correct bugs as early as possible.
- **Verification:** Verify correct operation by checking for unintended bugs and faults as well as malicious manipulations such as hardware Trojans.
- **Safety:** Avert physical and economical harm from people and business respectively.
- **Security:** Prevent exploitation of vulnerabilities by building secure systems.
- **Trustworthiness:** The degree to which the behavior of hardware is verifiable compliant with its stated functionality.

- Trust: The degree to which a stakeholder believes in the trustworthiness of a component. Note that this does not imply that the component is indeed trustworthy.
- Accountability: Assurance that an individual or an organization will be evaluated on their performance or behavior related to something for which they are responsible.
- Legal Compliance: Compliance with laws and regulations concerning hardware design, manufacturing, integration, and use.

Approaches

There exists a number approaches to ensure that hardware components are safe and trustworthy. Our goal is to determine how these existing approaches can be leveraged to contribute to the various desiderata introduced before. Please carefully read the description of each approach below:

- Trusted Manufacturing: Retain necessary manufacturing capabilities at domestic companies.
- Standards & Certifications: Standards by industry and government driven standardization bodies, certification of products and manufacturing sites.
- Open Hardware: Open-source hardware all the way from publicly available design files, open-source EDA tools, open gate libraries, ...
- Testing & Verification: Simulation, testing, and formal verification to detect bugs and manipulations.
- Physical Analysis: Invasive or destructive analysis of a piece of hardware through reverse engineering, side-channel analysis, or fault injection to detect leakage of sensitive information or cause unintended behavior.

- 11) From your professional perspective, **how important** is each **requirement** for the respective **stakeholder**? 1 - not at all important 2 - slightly important 3 - moderately important 4 - very important 5 - extremely important *[For each cell of the table, please fill in a number between 1 and 5 according to the scale below. Use the "TAB" key to speed up the process. If you feel unable to provide an estimation, feel free to leave the respective cell empty.]*

[Row items:] ◦ Designers ◦ Manufacturers ◦ System Integrators ◦ Policy Makers & Watchdogs ◦ End Users
[Column items:] ◦ Verification ◦ Safety ◦ Debuggability ◦ Trustworthiness ◦ Legal Compliance ◦ Accountability ◦ Security ◦ Trust

- 12) From your professional perspective, **how applicable** is each **approach** to the respective **stakeholder**? 1 - not at all applicable 2 - slightly applicable 3 - moderately applicable 4 - very applicable 5 - extremely applicable *[For each cell of the table, please fill in a number between 1 and 5 according to the scale below. Use the "TAB" key to speed up the process. If you feel unable to provide an estimation, feel free to leave the respective cell empty.]*

[Row items:] ◦ Designers ◦ Manufacturers ◦ System Integrators ◦ Policy Makers & Watchdogs ◦ End Users
[Column items:] ◦ Trusted Manufacturing ◦ Standards & Certifications ◦ Open Hardware ◦ Testing & Verification ◦ Physical Analysis

- 13) From your professional perspective, **how useful** is each **approach** to satisfy the respective **requirement**? 1 - not at all useful 2 - slightly useful 3 - moderately useful 4 - very useful 5 - extremely useful *[For each cell of the table, please fill in a number between 1 and 5 according to the scale below. Use the "TAB" key to speed up the process. If you feel unable to provide an estimation, feel free to leave the respective cell empty.]*

[Row items:] ◦ Verification ◦ Safety ◦ Debuggability ◦ Trustworthiness ◦ Legal Compliance ◦ Accountability ◦ Security ◦ Trust
[Column items:] ◦ Trusted Manufacturing ◦ Standards & Certifications ◦ Open Hardware ◦ Testing & Verification ◦ Physical Analysis

D. Previous Experience

- 14) How familiar are you with the following aspects of hardware in general?

[Row items:] ◦ 1 - not at all familiar ◦ 2 - slightly familiar ◦ 3 - somewhat familiar ◦ 4 - moderately familiar ◦ 5 - extremely familiar ◦ No answer

[Column items:] ◦ Hardware Design ◦ Hardware Manufacturing ◦ Hardware EDA Tools ◦ Hardware Architecture ◦ Hardware IP Protection

- 15) How familiar are you with the following approaches for hardware reliability, trust, and security?

[Row items:] ◦ 1 - not at all familiar ◦ 2 - slightly familiar ◦ 3 - somewhat familiar ◦ 4 - moderately familiar ◦ 5 - extremely familiar ◦ no answer

[Column items:] ◦ Side-Channel & Fault Analysis ◦ Open-Source Hardware ◦ Hardware Reverse Engineering ◦ Trusted Manufacturing & Split Manufacturing ◦ Hardware Simulation, Testing & Verification ◦ Hardware Standards & Certifications

E. Outro

- 16) Do you want to add anything to this survey that you think might be relevant to our work? *[free text]*
 17) Do you have any feedback regarding the survey? *[free text]*

Thank you for participating in our study! We would like to thank you very much for your cooperation. The questionnaire has been completed and your input has been saved. If you have any questions about this study, please feel free to contact us: julian.speith@mpi-sp.org, steffen.becker@mpi-sp.org. You can now close the browser window.

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